

Aroma variations of mid-Atlantic hops driven by growing regions and postharvest practices

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Abstract

Hop (*Humulus lupulus* L.) is an indispensable raw material with unique bitterness and pleasant aroma in the brewing industry. Recently, hop has become an emerging specialty crop in Mid-Atlantic regions due to the unprecedented development of the craft brewing. However, the aroma characteristics of these region-specific hops are not yet available. This study explored the aroma profiles of hops harvested from multiple mid-Atlantic locations and experienced various postharvest practices by use of headspace-solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry-olfactometry (HS-SPME-GC-MS-O). Results showed that β -myrcene, geraniol, linalool and methyl octanoate with respective herbal, citrus and floral notes were predominant compounds in all fresh and dried hops. Fresh Cascade and Chinook from Meadowview contained significantly higher concentrations for most aroma compounds comparing to the ones harvested from other locations. Dehydrator drying could effectively preserve aroma compounds in both varieties, especially when compared to oven drying. Additionally, freeze-drying maximally retained the original hop colour.

Keywords: hops, aroma, quality, growing regions, drying

Introduction

Hop plant is a vigorous, climbing and herbaceous perennial. It is primarily used as an imperative brewing ingredient due to its unique bitterness and pleasant aroma [1, 2]. The distinguishing bitterness mainly derives from the α -acids and β -acids from the lupulin glands of female hop cones. The “hoppy” aroma, however, is far away from being fully understood due to its extremely complicated composition. The unique aroma in hops is a result of the interaction among hundreds of volatile compounds, which are collectively known as hop essential oil [3]. The complexity behind hop essential oil has made aroma characterisation in hops a really challenging task.

Several Pacific Northwest states, like Washington, Oregon and Idaho, are the leading hop producers in US for decades. The hop production in mid-Atlantic regions has always been minor due to climate challenges like shorter day length and high heat and humidity [4, 5]. However, in recent years, following the fertiliser recommendations for economic hop production and the increasing consumer interest in locally-sourced ingredients, regional craft brewing industry is continuously blooming and hop has become an emerging specialty crop in mid-Atlantic states. Cascade and Chinook have been reported as the dominant hop varieties due to their resilient adaptability to the regional environment. Despite this, the aroma characteristics of region-specific hops are still unavailable.

Drying is the most commonly-used postharvest practice for hops to prevent the spoilage. It is well known that the temperature and oxygen levels involved in the drying process could greatly affect the aroma generation routes through oxidation, polymerization and Maillard reaction [6]. Therefore, understanding the influences of different drying practices on hop aroma behind these chemical transformations is of vital importance for the selection of appropriate postharvest applications for enhanced final quality of hop products.

This study aimed to investigate the aroma characteristics of Cascade and Chinook hops harvested from various mid-Atlantic locations and assess the impact of different postharvest practices on their aroma profiles by combined use of headspace-solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry-olfactometry (HS-SPME-GC-MS-O) and meticulous quantitation approaches.

Experimental

Sample preparation

Fresh Cascade hops were harvested from three farms located at Meadowview (MDV), Petersburg (PTB) and Blacksburg (BKB) in Virginia, US, respectively. Fresh Chinook hops were collected from the first two growing regions mentioned above. Both hop varieties were harvested at their optimal maturities during the 2019 harvesting season. Dehydrator drying, oven drying and freeze-drying were applied as three different postharvest practices to Meadowview Cascade and Chinook hops. All samples were dried down to a final moisture content between

8%~10% (wet basis). Dried hop cones were cooled at room temperature, transferred into odour-free sealing bags, sealed with a vacuum sealer (KOIOS Vacuum Sealer Machine, California, USA) and finally stored in a freezer (-80°C) until further analysis.

HS-SPME sampling

Frozen fresh and dried cones were ground for 1 min with a blender (Vitamix Explorian blender, Ohio, USA) prior to aroma analysis. Forty mg of fresh hop powder or 10 mg of dried hop powder were placed in a 20-mL amber SPME vial (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA). The vials were sealed with a PTFE-lined cap (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA) and equilibrated in the autosampler agitator (Leap Technologies Inc., Carrboro, NC, USA) for 10 min at 50°C with a stirring speed of 250 rpm. A preconditioned 1-cm 50/30 divinylbenzene/Carboxen/PDMS fibre (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA) was exposed to the headspace of the vial for an additional 30 min at 50°C prior to GC injection.

GC-MS-O analysis

The GC-MS-O system equipped with a 6890N GC (Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA), an 5975B MSD and a PHASER Olfactory Detection Port (GL Sciences, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) was used to analyse the aroma composition in hops. Separations were performed on a DB-WAX capillary column (30 m × 0.32 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness) (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA). Oven temperature was programmed from 40°C to 150°C at 5°C/min and then to 225°C at 20°C/min with an initial and final holding time of 5 and 20 min, respectively. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 2 ml/min. Conditions for the MSD were as follows: interface temperature, 230°C; ionization energy, 70 eV; mass range, 40~500 amu; EM voltage, Autotune +165 V; scan rate, 4.45 scans/s.

Three panellists (aged from 25 to 45) were selected to perform olfactometry analysis. All panellists have received at least 20 h of GC-O training by sniffing 25 aroma standards commonly found in hops. The retention time, odour descriptors, and intensities of all the perceivable odorants were recorded.

Quantitation

Stable isotope dilution analysis (SIDA) and standard addition method (SAM) were used for the quantitation of aroma-active compounds in hops. Isotopically labelled standards including 1.20 µg/µL [²H₂]-β-myrcene, 0.10 µg/µL [²H₃]-linalool, 0.10 µg/µL [²H₆]-geraniol, 0.05 µg/µL [²H₆]-geraniol acetate, 0.05 µg/µL [²H₁₅]-methyl octanoate and 0.01 µg/µL [²H₂]-cis-3-hexen-1-ol in methylene chloride were employed for accurate quantitation, with response factors of 0.9389, 1.0274, 0.8576, 1.2723, 1.3879 and 1.5775, respectively. The mixture of 0.73 µg/µL decane and 0.48 µg/µL 2-octanol in methanol was used as the internal standard for SAM. Peak area ratio and mass ratio of targeted aromas to internal standard were obtained to build calibration curves, which can be further applied for calculating the final concentrations of analytes.

Colour evaluation

Parameters relating to the colour of dried hops were determined using a hand-held colorimeter (Minolta Co., Ltd., Chiyoda, Tokyo, Japan) according to the International Commission on Illumination (CIE) colour coordinates *L**, *a** and *b**. Browning index, which is a reflection of the brown colour purity in hops, can be further calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Browning index (BI)} = \frac{100 \times \left(\frac{a^* + 1.75 \times L^*}{5.645 \times L^* + a^* - 3.012 \times b^*} \right) - 0.31}{0.17}$$

Results and discussion

A total of 33 aroma-active compounds were identified in five fresh Cascade and Chinook hops using HS-SPME-GC-MS-O. Tables 1 and 2 show the odour attributes and concentrations of selected aroma-active compounds in five fresh hop samples, respectively. Most of these aroma compounds exhibited fruity, sweet, floral and citrus notes except α-pinene and β-myrcene, which possessed piney, woody and herbal notes. All five samples expressed complex profiles with varied concentrations of aroma constituents. In general, both Meadowview Cascade and Meadowview Chinook contained significantly higher aroma concentrations for most of the compounds compared to their counterparts from other growing regions, which might be attributed to the advantageous climate condition, soil or agronomic practices from that particular growing site. In addition, L-calamenene and germacrene B were characteristic aroma compounds unique to Cascade and Chinook hops, respectively.

Table 1: Odour attributes of selected aroma-active compounds in fresh Cascade and Chinook hops.

No.	Aroma compounds	Odour description
1	2-Methylbutyl isovalerate	floral, fruity, berry, apple
2	Methyl octanoate	sweet, fruity, waxy, herbal, plastic
3	Methyl (4E)-4-nonenoate	fruity, citrus, lemon
4	α -Pinene	cedarwood, piney
5	β -Myrcene	balsamic, woody, herbal
6	trans- α -Bergamotene	sweet, floral, citrus
7	L-Calamenene	rosy, sweet, cinnamon
8	Germacrene B	rosy, sweet
9	Linalool	sweet, floral, orange
10	Geraniol	orange, citrus

Table 2: Concentrations of selected aroma-active compounds in fresh Cascade and Chinook hops¹.

No. ²	Concentration (μ g/g hops dry basis)				
	Ca-MDV	Ca-PTB	Ca-BKB	Ch-MDV	Ch-PTB
1	5.59 \pm 0.31 ^a	2.92 \pm 0.13 ^c	3.52 \pm 0.23 ^b	25.38 \pm 0.67 ^a	2.66 \pm 0.22 ^b
2	3.85 \pm 0.77 ^a	1.80 \pm 0.21 ^b	2.35 \pm 0.14 ^{ab}	11.36 \pm 2.21 ^a	5.46 \pm 0.17 ^a
3	5.02 \pm 0.07 ^a	2.41 \pm 0.08 ^c	3.10 \pm 0.21 ^b	5.36 \pm 0.06 ^a	1.93 \pm 0.17 ^b
4	2.79 \pm 0.29 ^a	2.82 \pm 0.13 ^a	2.70 \pm 0.25 ^a	4.36 \pm 0.67 ^a	1.04 \pm 0.04 ^b
5	1872.01 \pm 108.10 ^a	1384.89 \pm 151.81 ^a	1473.63 \pm 143.92 ^a	2121.68 \pm 101.56 ^a	418.79 \pm 31.61 ^b
6	54.98 \pm 3.66 ^a	35.27 \pm 0.74 ^b	38.97 \pm 7.99 ^b	132.33 \pm 9.78 ^a	11.57 \pm 1.92 ^b
7	0.15 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.19 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.17 \pm 0.02 ^{ab}	ND	ND
8	ND ³	ND	ND	308.57 \pm 37.70 ^a	23.74 \pm 5.34 ^b
9	25.24 \pm 0.74 ^a	17.10 \pm 1.43 ^b	18.61 \pm 0.35 ^b	23.29 \pm 0.99 ^a	11.08 \pm 0.54 ^b
10	9.65 \pm 0.02 ^a	6.48 \pm 0.45 ^b	8.44 \pm 0.30 ^a	44.52 \pm 1.49 ^a	3.35 \pm 0.30 ^b

¹ Ca: Cascade; Ch: Chinook; MDV: Meadowview; PTB: Petersburg; BKB: Blacksburg;

² The number is corresponding to the aroma compounds in Table 1;

³ ND: Not detected;

Within the same hop variety, values of concentration followed by same superscript letter in the same row were not significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

According to the HS-SPME-GC-MS-O results, a total of 35 aroma-active compounds were identified in dried Meadowview Cascade and Chinook hops. Table 3 exhibited the odour characteristics of the 9 most important compounds in dried hops. In addition to β -myrcene and β -ocimene that were perceived as woody, herbal, smoky and earthy notes, other aroma compounds possessed typical floral, fruity, sweet and citrus odour impressions. The concentrations of the above-mentioned aroma-active compounds were shown in Table 4. The dehydrator-dried hops showed significantly higher aroma concentrations for most of the compounds in both varieties, followed by freeze-dried hops and then oven-dried ones. Linalool and geraniol were two exceptions in Meadowview Chinook hops, in which significantly higher contents of these two compounds were observed after freeze-drying. Freeze-drying is usually considered as a reliable approach to circumvent thermal degradation and achieve excellent aroma retention in food products. However, in this study, freeze-drying only led to intermediate content levels for most aromas among three drying practices. This might be ascribed to the pressure reduction in the drying chamber that might have led to considerable loss of volatile compounds with low-boiling points to the environment [7].

Table 3: Odour attributes of selected aroma-active compounds in dried Cascade and Chinook hops.

No.	Aroma compounds	Odour description
1	Methyl octanoate	floral, sweet, fruity
2	Geranyl propionate	floral, rose, waxy
3	β -Myrcene	balsamic, woody, herbal
4	β -Ocimene	earthy, smoky, green
5	trans- α -Bergamotene	sweet, floral, citrus
6	Germacrene B	rose, sweet
7	L-Calamenene	rose, sweet, cinnamon
8	Linalool	sweet, floral, orange
9	Geraniol	orange, citrus

Table 4: Concentrations of selected aroma-active compounds in dried Cascade and Chinook hops¹.

No. ²	Ca-MDV			Ch-MDV		
	DD	OD	FD	DD	OD	FD
1	8.10±0.07 ^a	6.11±0.38 ^a	7.02±0.78 ^a	20.70±0.76 ^a	19.13±1.17 ^b	30.42±0.85 ^b
2	9.83±0.07 ^a	8.12±0.86 ^b	8.11±0.75 ^b	8.59±0.75 ^a	7.09±0.89 ^{ab}	6.82±0.28 ^b
3	2333.52±110.53 ^a	1750.02±141.12 ^b	2069.47±129.80 ^{ab}	3122.19±105.82 ^a	2839.74±195.33 ^a	2678.52±232.53 ^a
4	13.94±0.46 ^a	11.83±0.54 ^b	12.35±1.00 ^{ab}	15.28±0.62 ^a	12.28±0.60 ^b	13.17±0.48 ^b
5	37.23±1.53 ^a	30.73±1.24 ^b	30.98±2.06 ^b	104.41±7.06 ^a	82.41±6.07 ^b	82.59±1.57 ^b
6	ND ³	ND	ND	77.46±5.53 ^a	53.70±5.05 ^b	63.65±1.05 ^b
7	0.12±0.00 ^a	0.11±0.00 ^a	0.11±0.00 ^a	ND	ND	ND
8	16.68±1.77 ^a	10.89±0.23 ^b	15.53±0.12 ^a	18.45±0.56 ^b	16.70±0.75 ^c	26.26±0.77 ^a
9	9.65±0.44 ^a	7.39±0.37 ^a	9.10±1.00 ^a	74.49±2.66 ^b	53.79±4.43 ^c	98.71±0.18 ^a

¹ Ca: Cascade; Ch: Chinook; MDV: Meadowview; PTB: Petersburg; BKB: Blacksburg; DD: Dehydrator drying; OD: Oven drying; FD: Freeze-drying

² The number is corresponding to the aroma compounds in Table 3;

³ ND: Not detected

Within each hop variety, values of concentration followed by same superscript letter in the same row were not significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Principal component analysis was applied in this study to further understand the difference in aroma profiles of fresh and dried hops. Figure 1a shows the score plot for all fresh hops in triplicates. The only overlap observed were Blacksburg and Petersburg Cascade hops, suggesting certain similarity in their aroma profiles. Both Meadowview Cascade and Chinook hops were well separated from their counterparts, demonstrating their unique aroma characteristics. This is in agreement with the quantitation results. According to the score plot for dried hop samples (Figure 1b), different drying techniques resulted in dissimilarity of aroma compositions in hops. Dehydrator-dried hops could be clearly discriminated from corresponding oven-dried and freeze-dried ones, whereas the latter two were overlapped for both hop varieties. This indicated the distinguishing aroma profile in dehydrator-dried hops.

Figure 1: Principal component score plot of (a) five fresh hops and (b) dried hops based on the concentrations of selected aroma-active compounds. Ca: Cascade; Ch: Chinook; MDV: Meadowview; PTB: Petersburg; BKB: Blacksburg; DD: Dehydrator drying; OD: Oven drying; FD: Freeze-drying.

From a consumer-acceptance point of view, colour is an important attribute to determine the quality of dried products, therefore the colour of dried hops was also evaluated (Table 5). As expected, freeze-drying could provide both varieties with the highest L^* and b^* and the lowest a^* and BI values, followed by dehydrator drying and then oven drying. In other words, among all the drying practices, freeze-drying could minimise the green colour degradation and retain the original hues of hops most effectively. The reason for the better performance of freeze-drying might be ascribed to its lower possessing temperature, which can prevent the nonenzymatic browning and provide the maximum retention of chlorophyll in hops [8]. However, freeze-drying is a costly process and its operation requires high-energy consumption. To this end, dehydrator drying is an overall appropriate drying practice for small-size hop growers due to its decent aroma and colour retention as well as low initial investment and energy consumption.

Table 5: Colour evaluation of dried Cascade and Chinook hops¹.

Colour Attributes ²	Ca-MDV			Ch-MDV		
	DD	OD	FD	DD	OD	FD
<i>L</i> [*]	15.18±0.30 ^b	13.30±0.45 ^c	17.87±0.15 ^a	13.02±0.31 ^b	12.86±0.21 ^b	17.34±0.26 ^a
<i>a</i> [*]	-2.28±0.28 ^b	-0.15±0.07 ^a	-4.23±0.17 ^c	-0.90±0.05 ^b	1.10±0.08 ^a	-3.55±0.10 ^c
<i>b</i> [*]	16.27±0.40 ^a	15.68±0.15 ^a	16.53±0.49 ^a	16.56±0.15 ^a	16.47±0.14 ^{ab}	16.16±0.11 ^b
BI	233.41±14.34 ^b	309.45±21.58 ^a	157.27±8.89 ^c	385.41±21.58 ^a	395.42±27.36 ^a	162.87±5.37 ^b

¹ Ca: Cascade; Ch: Chinook; MDV: Meadowview; PTB: Petersburg; BKB: Blacksburg; DD: Dehydrator drying; OD: Oven drying; FD: Freeze-drying

² *L*^{*}: 0 (black) to 100 (white); *a*^{*}: +60 (red) to -60 (green); *b*^{*}: +60 (yellow) to -60 (blue); BI: Browning Index, brown colour purity; Within each hop variety, values with same superscript letter in the same row were not significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

All fresh samples investigated in this study exhibited distinctive aroma profiles, which might have been attributed not only to varietal difference, but also to other environmental and agronomical factors at different growing sites. Predominant components detected were responsible for typical herbal, sweet and citrus notes. Both varieties from Meadowview farm exhibited the highest concentrations for most aroma compounds, indicating a potential location advantage. Dehydrator drying was able to retain higher aroma concentrations compared to oven and freeze-drying, therefore was considered as a desirable drying practice for small-size hop growers to enhance the quality of final hop products.

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